

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-HEALING TECHNIQUES FOR FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES: RECENT ADVANCES ON INTRINSIC SELF-HEALING MECHANISM

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Keywords: CFRPs, Self-healing, Thermoplastics, Diels Alder reaction, Supramolecular polymers

ABSTRACT

Recent advances made by the Applied Mechanics Laboratory (AML/UoP) group in the field of intrinsic self-healing mechanisms for structural composites are briefly reviewed in this paper. Three different types of reversible polymeric systems have been studied so far as potential self-healing agents (SHA) into carbon fibre epoxy composites (CFRPs); common thermoplastics such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyamides (nylon-66), bis-maleimides (BMI) based on Diels Alder (DA) reaction, and supramolecular polymers (SP). These SHA have been integrated into CFRPs by utilizing a variety of methodologies (i.e., blending, interleaving, prepregging, etc). A thorough experimental campaign containing mode I and II fracture, three-point bending (3PB), compression before impact (CBI), low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) tests, for all the aforementioned SHA-modified composites, has been completed to assess potential knock-down effects and the healing capabilities of the composites. The test program was complemented by optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) examinations and the monitoring of the acoustic emission (AE) activity of the samples during testing, which led to qualitative conclusions regarding the involved failure and healing mechanisms. The key-results and achievements of the whole work are outlined in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, fibre reinforced composites (FRPs) are year by year replacing metals due to their high specific stiffness and high strength in combination with corrosion resistance. However, during their service life, these composites appear matrix cracking and delaminations between the reinforcing plies due to their laminated structure. A primary limitation of these composites is the poor interlaminar toughness and strength. The mismatch of anisotropic mechanical and thermal properties in between plies of different principal directions promotes out-of-plane stresses at the edges of the structures as well as in the case of stringer run out, thickness variation, holes and structural stiffeners joined to composite skin, and are only some of the candidate areas for delamination under in-plane and out-of-plane loadings. Delaminations are among the most frequent modes of failure encountered in laminated composites [1, 2] and are resulted either from fatigue loadings or LVI events.

Conventional repair techniques of composites are expensive, require extensive labor force, and cannot repair defects deep inside the material. Self-healing polymers [3] is an approach which has not yet been incorporated to commercial composites but promises to face some principal weak points. This smart technology aims to in-situ repair matrix cracks and matrix/reinforcement debonding and thus to extend the effective life-span of the composites, to reduce the maintenance needs and costs and to improve the damage tolerance and reliability of composite structures. Self-healing composites have previously been developed by embedding SHA into the matrix using microcapsules or vascular networks, [4, 5] that will release the SHA upon crack damage. A different approach towards self-healing composites is matrices that comprise reversible polymers [6, 7] that are able to proceed with multiply healing cycles at the same damaged site.

The present paper is intended to outline recent progresses achieved by the AML/UoP research group in the field of intrinsic self-healing mechanism [8-14]. The aim of the paper is not to comprehensively report all the results but to summarize and compare some key-achievements.

The ultimate goal of the work reviewed here in was the development and evaluation of intrinsic self-healing techniques for CFRPs. These techniques were developed by the incorporation of reversible polymers directly into the epoxy matrix. In other words, the non autonomous strategy [6, 7] was utilized, as an external stimulus (i.e., heat) is required to activate the healing process. Three types of SHA on the basis of their chemistry have been explored (Fig. 1); Common thermoplastics based on covalent bonding, BMI polymers based on DA reaction and hydrogen bonded SP based on supramolecular chemistry. Various SHA forms and integration methods of the SHA into composite architecture were studied. The work reviewed here aimed to experimentally study the potential knock-down effects on the mechanical properties, the healing capabilities, and the healing mechanisms of these healable composites. The experimental campaign included mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, 3PB, CBI, LVI and CAI tests (Fig. 2).

2 MATERIALS, MANUFACTURING PROCESSES AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Three different types of thermally reversible polymeric systems (classified based on their chemistry) have been examined so far as potential SHA into CFRPs (Fig. 1a); (a) Common thermoplastics, such as PET and nylon-66, based on reversible covalent bonds (Fig. 1a-i), (b) BMI-based polymers, based on DA and retro-DA reactions through special covalent bonds (Fig. 1a-ii), and (c) SP, based on hydrogen bonds (Fig. 1a-iii).

The PET thermoplastic polymer was supplied in pellet form by NGP, Greece [8]. The commercial copolymer nylon (Griltex D 1330A, supplied by EMS-Griltech, Switzerland) was used in two versions; undoped and doped with 10 wt. % multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) [9]. Also, SHA blends containing 20% or 25% BMI polymer (BMI prepolymer) were supplied by TNO, The Netherlands. More information about the BMI prepolymer-based SHA is found in [15]. The "homemade" pure BMI polymer was synthesized in-house as described in [11] and was utilized to impregnate carbon fabric pre-forms. Finally, the SP material, based on a low- T_g (-66 °C) polymer modified with UPy-moieties, was supplied by Suprapolix BV, The Netherlands [10].

For the CFRPs modified with the thermoplastic SHA, the epoxy system that was utilized to impregnate woven fabrics was the L/EPH 161 (resin/hardener) and was supplied by R&G, Germany. The woven carbon fabric was supplied by Sigma Aldrich, Germany, having a specific weight of 280 gr/m². The CFRPs modified with all the other SHA were manufactured by utilizing the commercial aerospace-grade unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre-epoxy prepreg tape CE-1007 150-38, supplied by SGL Group, Germany.

2.2 Self-healing agents (SHA) processing and composite integration methods

A variety of SHA forms (i.e., micro-particles [8], thin films [10, 14], electrospun veils [12], etc) and also a variety of methodologies for the modification of the CFRPs using the aforementioned SHA (i.e., blending [8], prepregging [11], interleaving [10, 14], etc) have been studied so far. In addition, the SHA were incorporated in various places through-the-thickness of the laminate composites.

Fig. 1b summarizes the various SHA forms (Fig. 1b-i) and SHA integration methods into composite architecture (Fig. 1b-ii). The topologies of the SHA into composite laminates are shown in Fig. 1c.

Figure 1: (a) The thermally reversible self-healing agents (SHA) utilized in the present investigation, classified based on their chemistries. (b) SHA processing and forms (b-i) and composite integration methods (b-ii). (c) Design of the composite laminates.

2.2.1 Thermoplastics (PET and nylon) – Mode I and II fracture tests

Thermoplastic micro-particles (PET or nylon) were blended at the quantity of 7 wt. % into the epoxy matrix and mixing by hand was followed. Unmodified and modified matrices were used to manufacture CFRP plates of 16 woven plies each and cross-ply stacking pattern. Two types of composites were manufactured; the reference one without any SHA and the modified ones containing thermoplastic micro-particles (PET or MWCNTs doped or undoped nylon), having an average particle diameter of 80-120 μm . Following hand lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured for 24 h at ambient temperature, followed by a post-cure regime of 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 h.

2.2.2 Thermoplastics (nylon) – Low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) tests

Three types of quasi-isotropic laminates with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ were manufactured; the reference laminate, the modified laminate with two nylon electrospun veils, and the modified laminate with two 2 wt. % MWCNTs doped nylon electrospun veils. Both undoped and doped electrospun veils were randomly oriented with circular shape having a diameter of approximately 80 μm . Following the lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave for 5 h at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 6 bars applied pressure.

2.2.3 Bismaleimides – Mode I and II fracture tests

2.2.3.1 BMI prepolymer grains

Five types of laminates with 22 UD plies each were prepared; the reference laminate and four modified laminates containing 60, 120, 180 and 240 grams per square meters (gsm) SHA in their mid-plane. The SHA created an “interleaf” in the mid-plane of the composite. Following lamination, the composites were vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave.

Two curing cycles were examined; (a) at 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 6 bars for 2 h, according to manufacturers' recommendation, and (b) at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 4 bars for 5 h, based on previous DSC measurements. The lower curing pressure of the curing cycle (b) was selected to minimize the diffusion of the SHA from the mid-plane to the upper and lower neighboring plies, a phenomenon clearly observed in [11].

2.2.3.2 BMI prepregs

Two UD laminated plates with 22 plies each were manufactured; the reference laminate and the modified laminate with two BMI-based prepregs on the mid-plane. Following the lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave.

2.2.4 Bismaleimides – Low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) tests

Three types of quasi-isotropic laminated plates with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ were manufactured; (a) the reference laminate, (b) the modified laminate with BMI prepolymer grains between the primary layers of the CFRP, and (c) the modified laminate with two pure BMI prepregs. For both types of BMI-based SHA, their placement into composite architecture is sketched in Fig. 1c. Following the lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave at 130 °C and 6 bars for 2 h.

2.2.5 Supramolecular – Mode I and II fracture tests

Two UD laminates made out of 22 plies were manufactured; the reference laminate and the modified laminate containing the SP interleaves at the mid-plane. Following the lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in autoclave at 130 °C and 6 bars for 2 h.

2.2.6 Supramolecular – Low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) tests

Three types of quasi-isotropic laminated plates containing 16 plies each, with $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ stacking sequence were manufactured; (a) the reference laminate, (b) the modified laminate with SP interleaves and (c) the modified laminate with two SP prepregs, both placed symmetrically into the composite. For both modified composites, the SP interleaves were placed into composite architecture as seen in Fig. 1c. Following the lay-up, the laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in autoclave at 130 °C and 6 bars for 2 h.

2.3 Experimental methods

A thorough test campaign has been scheduled and realized, which contained mechanical tests, non-destructive inspections and material morphology examinations. The assessment of potential knock-down effects and the healing capability of the SHA-modified composites were investigated under mode I and II fracture (Fig. 2a), LVI, CAI (Fig. 2b) and 3PB (Fig. 2c) tests. Also, optical microscopy and SEM examinations were conducted, and the AE activities of the samples during tests were monitored.

2.3.1 Mode I and II interlaminar fracture toughness tests

Quasi-static mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests (Fig. 2a-i) were performed at a 25 kN Instron UTM using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) method, according to the AITM 1.0005 standard. The information about the test is referred in [10]. The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (Fig. 2a-ii) was measured using the three-point end-notched flexure (ENF) method, according to the AITM 1.0006 standard. The details on these tests can be found in [14]. After the first fracture, healing was activated by applying the healing cycles presented in paragraph 2.4. Then, the tests were repeated to examine the H.E. of the various SHA-modified composites.

2.3.2 Low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) tests

CBI, LVI, and CAI tests were performed according to the AITM1-0010: 2015 standard using an in-house constructed guided drop weight tester. The selected impact energy was that of 25 J. After impact, the induced damages for each composite type were evaluated using C-scan. After C-scan, the samples were subjected to the healing cycle (see paragraph 2.4). CAI tests were carried out at a 250 kN Instron machine to evaluate the residual compressive strength of the damaged CFRPs before vs. after the healing process. More details are reported in [9].

2.3.3 Three-point bending (3PB) tests

3PB tests were carried out following the ASTM D7264M-07 in an Instron test frame, by applying center loading on a simple supported beam (Fig. 2c). The load and corresponding mid-span deflection were continuously recorded until the failure occurred. The flexural stiffness (E_{flex}) and flexural strength (σ_{max}) were the output magnitudes. More details are reported in [13].

2.3.4 Acoustic emission (AE), optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

During the mode I, mode II, CBI and CAI tests, the AE activities of the specimens were recorded in-situ; a transducer was mounded on the each specimens' surface (Fig. 2a, b), using a layer of a suitable gel been applied between the transducer and the specimen to provide acoustic coupling. The relevant information is provided in [9-11, 14]. For all these tests, AE was utilized as a complementary non-destructive technique towards the extraction of useful conclusions regarding the damage accumulation processes.

Optical microscopy examinations on cross-sections and fracture surfaces of the composites were performed using an inverted metallurgical microscope, in order the effects of the various SHA in composite's architecture and also the crack propagation mechanisms to be identified. SEM examinations were also conducted. More details are found in [9].

The melting temperatures (T_m) of the bulk SHA were measured using the Perkin-Elmer DSC 8500 differential scanning calorimeter, in order the healing temperatures of the composites after first fracture to be determined.

Figure 2: An overview of the utilized characterization methods. (a) Mode I (i) and Mode II (ii) interlaminar fracture toughness tests. (b) Low-velocity impact (LVI) (i) and compression-after-impact (CAI) (ii) tests. (c) Three-point bending (3PB) tests.

2.4 Healing processes and healing efficiencies (H.E.) calculation formulas

After first failure under mode I or II or LVI, the specimens were subjected to a simple healing cycle of heating under controlled through-the-thickness compression. The characteristics of the healing cycle for each material group are summarized in Table 1. The healing temperatures were chosen based on previous in-house DSC measurements. The compressive loading value was chosen as the minimum necessary to ensure that the adjacent crack flanks were kept in close proximity during healing activation. The loading values were chosen as the minimum necessary to ensure that the

adjacent crack flanks were kept in intimate contact during the healing procedure. Then, the samples were left to cool-down at room temperature. After the healing cycle, the samples were tested again using the same configurations.

The calculations of the healing efficiency (H.E.) of every system were based on Eq. (1a) and (1b):

$$\text{Mode I, II: H.E.} = (a_{\text{healed}}/a_{\text{modified}}) \cdot 100 (\%) \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{LVI: H.E.} = (A_{\text{healed}}/A_{\text{damaged}}) \cdot 100 (\%) \quad (1b)$$

where a or A (i.e., damage area) is the property under examination. a_{healed} and a_{modified} are the values of the property after healing and before healing, respectively. A_{healed} and A_{damaged} are the values of the property after healing and after LVI testing, respectively.

Material	Test	Healing cycle	T_m (°C)	Number of healing cycles
PET	Mode I & II	235 °C, 1kN, 10 min	230	1
Nylon	Mode I & II	235 °C, 1 kN, 5 min	230	4
Nylon electrospun	LVI	150 °C, 5 kN, 15 min	61	1
BMI prepolymer (20%)	Mode I & II	150 °C, 1 kN, 5 min	111	2
Pure BMI prepregs	Mode I & II	130 °C, 1 kN, 15 min	110	5
BMI prepolymer (25%)	LVI	150 °C, 5 kN, 7 min	111	1
Pure BMI prepregs	LVI	130 °C, 5 kN, 15 min	110	1
SP film	Mode I & II	100 °C, 1 kN, 15 min	77	7
SP film/prepreg	LVI	100 °C, 5 kN, 15 min	77	1

Table 1: Healing process characteristics for the various material groups tested.

The application of high healing temperatures may appear to be an issue not only for material's integrity but also for commercial implementation. On the other hand, the application of such temperatures for a short time period, which is the case here, is expected not to create any concerns to the materials, and also it saves time during the repair process. The process of thermally triggered healing and then testing was repeated several times for both mode I and II fracture tests, in order to assess the potential of the SHA for multiple repair events.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is obvious that the introduction of the SHA into composite architecture impacts upon many material properties. An overview of the effects of the various SHA studied on the interlaminar fracture toughnesses of the composites is presented in paragraph 3.1. In paragraph 3.2 the LVI and CAI performances of the SHA modified composites are compared. In paragraph 3.3 some certain results concerning the toughening and healing mechanisms are outlined. The effects of the SHA on the in-plane mechanical properties and on the AE activity during fracture tests are discussed in paragraphs 3.4 and 3.5. Finally, paragraph 3.6 briefly discusses the results and paragraph 3.7 provides an outlook.

3.1 Mode I and II interlaminar fracture toughness properties

PET thermoplastic micro-particles offer poor mode I toughening and healing properties as SHA into the final composite but significantly enhanced mode II fracture properties [8]. On the contrary, copolymer nylon micro-particles significantly enhanced the mode I and II fracture properties, with the MWCNTs-doped ones to offer the higher fracture toughness values [9]. Even better, after first fracture and healing, the nylon-modified composites exhibited high H.E. with a repeatable manner (Fig. 3a, b) [9].

Test results for composites containing DA-based SHA showed the ability of these SHA to enhance the mode I and II fracture toughness of the composite. The samples modified with pure BMI-based

prepregs performed the higher toughness [11]. The composites modified with BMI prepolymer exhibited moderate H.E. values (Fig. 3c), with these values to increase after curing of the samples in temperatures lower than the T_m [9]. Nevertheless, these temperatures slightly decreased the mode I fracture toughness of the composite [9].

According to experimental results for mendable composites containing SP as SHAs, it was shown that SP was able to considerably enhance the mode I [10] and II [14] interlaminar fracture toughness properties of the composites. As a characteristic example, the G_{IC} was increased by more than one order of magnitude (1550%) [10]. In addition, these modified samples exhibited high recoveries after first fracture for both mode I and II fracture toughness characteristics, while mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties were higher than the reference values, even after 7 healing activations [10].

Figure 3: Some representative results from the interlaminar fracture toughness tests. (a) Results from the mode I tests of the undoped (i) or doped (ii) modified CFRPs with nylon micro-particles before and after four healing cycles. (b) Results from the mode II tests of the undoped (i) or doped (ii) modified CFRPs with nylon micro-particles before and after four healing cycles. (c) Results from mode I tests before and after two consecutive healing cycles for samples containing BMI prepolymer, 120 gsm, cured in first curing cycle (130 °C) (i) and in second curing cycle (100 °C) (ii). Healing efficiency (H.E.) values (%) for the aforementioned modified composites are given to the right.

3.2 Low velocity impact (LVI) and compression after impact (CAI) properties

LVI and CAI test results for composites containing MWCNTs-doped or -undoped nylon electrospun nanofibrous veils as SHA are promising. As it was shown, the doped nylon modified composites exhibited comparable resistance to LVI with the undoped ones, while also an ability to enhance the E_{comp} of the entire laminate to a certain extent [9]. After LVI and following the healing

cycles presented in Table 1, all modified composites achieved 100% H.E. for the damage areas (Fig. 4a). After healing, the modified plates exhibited increased CAI properties, when compared with both the unhealed and the impacted reference ones [9].

In the case of the BMI-modified CFRPs, potential knock-down effects and the healing capability of these samples were examined under LVI and CAI tests, respectively. Firstly, the incorporation of the SHA into the matrix slightly decreased the compression properties of the unimpacted samples while exhibited less resistance to LVI [9]. After healing, pure BMI prepreg modified composites were able to heal the entire damage and to restore part of its mechanical properties [9]. On the other hand, samples containing BMI prepolymer were not able to heal the entire damage (Fig. 4b) as a result not to be able to restore their mechanical properties [9].

For the assessment of LVI behaviour of SP modified CFRPs, SP prepregs were fabricated in order the incorporation of the SHA into the composite to be simplified. Samples containing SP film (initial form) and prepreg were examined under LVI and CAI tests and compared (Fig. 4c). First of all, it was shown that by the incorporation of both SP forms into composite architecture the compression properties of the CFRPs were decreased with samples containing the SP prepregs to exhibit the higher degradation. After LVI tests, samples containing SP prepregs exhibited higher resistance to damage if compared with the reference (80% lower damage area) and SP film modified samples. Healing process revealed that SP SHA was not able to fully fill the damage into the composite. Despite the fact that 100% healing was not achieved, SP prepreg modified samples exhibited slightly improved compression characteristics after the healing cycle.

Some representative C-scan inspection images of composite plates modified with various SHA in the before LVI, after LVI and after healing situations are synopsisized in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Indicative C-scan inspection images before the LVI testing (left), after the LVI (middle) and after the healing process (right), of the modified CFRP with (a) 2% MWCNT doped nylon nanofibres, (b) pure BMI prepregs and (c) SP prepregs.

3.3 Materials morphology, toughening and healing mechanisms

By the incorporation of the PET or nylon thermoplastic micro-particles into the epoxy resin, the viscosities of the resulting mixtures were considerably increased, which made it difficult for the modified matrix materials to effectively infiltrate the reinforcing plies during lamination and occupy all the spaces between the layers [8, 9]. Thus, the thicknesses of the entire PET or nylon modified

composites were increased. As Fig. 5a shows, the thermoplastics were remained positioned into the matrix-rich interply layers of the CFRPs. The fracture toughness behaviours of the modified samples under both mode I and II fracture loadings were heavily relying to the micro-particles located in the mid-plane interlaminar regions. After mode I tests, the crack paths were complex; they deflected around micro-particles due to poor bonding between them and epoxy (Fig. 5a). Under mode II, the shear stresses induced to the crack tip caused plastic deformation to the mid-plane particles. After first fracture, the thermoplastic additive is the only one material that takes part in the healing process and heals the crack. The healing is achieved by melting and viscous flow of the thermoplastic into the crack plane. Then, the total of the fracture toughness recovery comes from the adhesive properties of the thermoplastic (PET or nylon) material.

BMI polymers, utilized in both powder and prepolymer forms, are characterized by fine adhesion properties with carbon fibres and also by high peel resistance [11]. Thus, the significant toughness increases for the BMI-modified composites are strongly attributed to the BMI material's ductile behaviour during mode I loading. At a first glance, the interface between the BMI and the epoxy matrix seems to be coherent and strong (Fig. 5b). During autoclave manufacturing, the BMI diffuses into the closest upper carbon epoxy layers (Fig. 5b). An analogous diffusion process was carried out for the BMI-impregnated layers, in which the epoxy system has been diffused. The diffusion of the epoxy system into the BMI-impregnated layers caused greater plastic deformation during mode I tests, resulting in increased fracture toughness characteristics [11].

The significant toughness increase observed for the SP modified composites is attributed to the enhanced supramolecular material interface with the epoxy matrix, which is extremely strong thereby forming strong bonding between the SP polymer and the epoxy. Infiltration by the SP into the epoxy matrix is evident in Fig. 5c. The modified composites clearly show ductile fracture behaviour. This behaviour reveals the strong bonding of the supramolecular interleaf with both the matrix and the carbon fibres.

Figure 5: Optical microscopy images of the cross-sections of various SHA-modified composites. (a) Thermoplastic micro-particles (PET or nylon) modified CFRPs [8, 9]. (b) Diels Alder (DA) based modified CFRPs [9, 11]. (c) Supramolecular polymer (SP) modified CFRPs [10, 12].

3.4 Knock-down effects on in-plane mechanical properties

As a parallel study, the knock-down effect of the various SHA incorporation into composite architectures were investigated by conducting 3PB [9, 13] and CBI [9] tests. In Table 2, some indicative decreases in flexural properties (E_{flex} and σ_{max}) under 3PB have been collected for 4 representative material types. The dispersion of the SHA in the entire matrix material of the composite strongly deteriorates the in-plane properties, which is the case for the PET and nylon [9, 13] modified CFRPs. On the contrary, the insert of a thin film (BMI powder [9] and SP interleaf [9]) in the mid-plane has a significant lesser effect on the in-plane properties of the composite.

Material	SHA form & integration	E_{flex}	σ_{max}
Nylon, doped	Particles, dispersed – entire matrix	60	61
BMI powder, 120 gsm	Powder, mid-plane interleaved	1.6	12
BMI prepreg	Bulk polymer, two mid-plane plies	15	34
SP interleaf	Thin film, mid-plane interleaved	0.12	22.5

Table 2: Knock-down effects (% decrease) on flexural properties E_{flex} and σ_{max} for 4 representative material types [9].

3.5 Results from acoustic emission (AE) recordings

Fig. 6 shows the cumulative number of AE hits vs. crack length as calculated for four specific crack lengths for both the reference and the SP modified composite. These composites consist a representative paradigm for the needs of the present review paper, showing the effect of the ductile mid-plane interleaf on the AE activity of the composite. The general trend presented in Fig. 6 is also followed by the rest of the composites modified with the other SHA.

Apparently, the reference composite manifests much more intense AE activity. This is a strong indication that for the same crack length propagation the reference composite undergoes more damage events than the supramolecular modified composite i.e. it gets more damaged and thus emits more AE. This fully aligns with the fact that the supramolecular modified material is tougher.

In addition, the AE activity vs. crack length for the healed modified samples is summarized in Fig. 6 where the data from the first, third, sixth and seventh healing cycle are depicted. A significant decrease of AE activity is a solid indication of the fact that the H.E. as well as the ability of the material to partially remedy previously damaged sites in the vicinity of the crack path and thus produce new AE events (from the healed sites under re-loading) is finite and with a decreasing trend.

Figure 6: Representative AE results for the case of the SP-modified composite. (a) Cumulative acoustic emission (AE) hits vs. crack length for the reference and the modified CFRPs. (b) Cumulative acoustic emission (AE) hits vs. crack length (a) for the modified CFRP after the first, third, sixth and seventh healing cycle [10].

3.6 Discussion

The experimental results reported in [8-14] generally show that by the incorporation of all these SHA systems into composites, the interlaminar fracture toughnesses were significantly enhanced. Interestingly, the samples containing SP interleaves exhibited dramatically increased fracture toughness characteristics. Even better, the modified composites achieved typical H.E. values from 60 to 100% after one healing activation.

Also, the effect of the curing regime on the toughening and healing performance of the CFRPs containing BMI was found to be remarkable. It was shown that curing temperatures lower than the melting point of the SHA slightly decreased the fracture toughness characteristics, while increased the healing capabilities of these samples.

Low velocity impact tests revealed that samples containing supramolecular prepregs or nylon electrospun veils enabled by nanotechnology (in the direction of incorporating carbon nanotubes into electrospun fibres), as interleaves between the primary layers of the composite exhibited higher resistance to delamination and increased CAI characteristics after the application of the healing cycle.

Finally, AE recordings showed that by the incorporation of a ductile phase (i.e., SHA) into the composite the AE activity in terms of hits is typically reduced while both AE characteristics (hits and energy) are reduced after the application of the healing cycles.

3.7 Outlook

The intrinsic self-healing technologies reviewed in this paper are envisioned to be incorporated locally in the early failure regions and other highly stressed areas of aeronautical CFRP structures. Also, the self-healing technologies based on reversible polymers can be placed in known critical regions of structures where damages predominately occur, such as around drilled holes or on skin-stringer run-outs. These regions will take advantage of these repair mechanisms and do not represent the overall host matrix mechanical performance due to the knock-down effect of these polymers to the whole composite.

It is obvious that the characterization tests reviewed herein are not representative compare to the “real life service” of these materials but all this investigation is conducted in the name of self-healing research. The preliminary “model studies” prove the viability of the concept of incorporating the current SHAs into epoxy CFRPs. The scope of all these modified systems is considered for future implementation as parts in aerospace structures.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Recent advances by the AML/UoP research group on the intrinsic mechanism for incorporating a self-healing functionality into structural composites are reviewed in this paper. The main focus was to underline some characteristic results and achievements.

According to all these experimental campaign, it was shown that by the incorporation of all these SHAs to the composites the mode I and II fracture toughness characteristics were significantly increased with samples containing supramolecular interleaves to exhibit dramatically increased fracture toughness characteristics (e.g., G_{IC} increased with more than one order of magnitude at approximately 1550%). These modified composites exhibited H.E. values from 60% to 100% after the application of the first healing cycle. In addition the effect of the curing regime on the toughening and healing behaviour of CFRPs containing bismaleimide polymers was investigated.

It was shown that curing temperatures lower than the melting point of the SHA slightly decreased the fracture toughness characteristics while increased the healing capabilities of these samples. Low velocity impact tests revealed that samples containing supramolecular prepregs or MWCNT doped nylon electrospun veils as interleaves between the primary layers of the composite exhibited higher resistance to delamination and increased CAI characteristics after the application of the healing cycle.

Finally, AE recordings showed that by the incorporation of a ductile phase (i.e., SHA) into the composite the AE activity in terms of hits is typically reduced while both AE characteristics (hits and energy) was reduced after the application of the healing cycles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work reviewed herein has been funded by: (a) the EU FP7 Transport (including Aeronautics) Programme within the frame of the project: Self-healing polymers for concepts on self-repaired aeronautical composites HIPOCRATES (ACP3-GA-2013-605412). (b) the European Union (European Social Fund – ESF) and Greek national funds through the Operational Program “Education and Lifelong Learning” of the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) Research Funding Program THALES, within the frame of action ‘Investing in knowledge society through the European Social Fund’. (c) the Erasmus Placement Programme 2015-2016. Also, the authors thank Tony Bosman (Suprapolix BV), Hartmut Fisher (TNO) and Aggelos Christopoulos (NTUA) for the material supply.

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